

12 APPENDIX

12.1 Primitive Merge Resolution Types

We identify a set of primitive merge resolution patterns based on the analysis of the real-world merge conflict resolutions from GitHub. For a merge tuple $(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{M})$ with line-level conflicting regions $A_i, B_i, O_i, i=0\dots N$, and token-level conflicting regions a_j^i, b_j^i, o_j^i corresponding to a line-level conflict i , we define following nine basic merge resolution types which serve as labels for supervised classification task:

- (1) Take changes a_j^i proposed in program \mathcal{A} (developer branch A) as resolution,
- (2) Take changes b_j^i proposed in program \mathcal{B} as resolution,
- (3) Take changes o_j^i in the base reference program \mathcal{O} as resolution,
- (4) Take a string concatenation of changes in a_j^i and b_j^i as resolution,
- (5) Take a string concatenation of changes in b_j^i and a_j^i as resolution (reverse order as compared to the previous),
- (6) Take changes a_j^i proposed in program \mathcal{A} , excluding the lines also present in the base reference program \mathcal{O} , as resolution,
- (7) Take changes b_j^i proposed in program \mathcal{B} , excluding the lines present in the base, as resolution,
- (8) Take a string concatenation of changes in a_j^i and b_j^i , excluding the lines present in the base, as resolution,
- (9) Take a string concatenation of changes in b_j^i and a_j^i , excluding the lines present in the base, as resolution (reverse order as compared to the previous),

Our analysis shows that over 99% of all the merge conflicts can be represented using these labels. While the above nine resolution types are primitive, they form a basis sufficient to cover a large class of real-world merge resolutions in modern version control systems, including arbitrary combinations or interleavings of lines.

Fig. 5 shows the label distribution obtained for token-level differencing algorithm. It excludes trivial (“take ours” or “take theirs”) merge resolutions at line-level. Note, that “take A” merge resolution at token-level does not correspond to “take ours” or “take theirs” merge resolution strategy, and can map to any label at line-level, thus representing a non-trivial merge scenario stimulating for machine learning studies.

The “Remove base” category combines the four primitive merge patterns that remove the lines present in the base branch from the resolution (e.g. take changes proposed in one program and exclude the lines present in base).

It is important to stress, these primitive merge resolution types at token-level are not strictly defined *templates* dictating which syntactic structures should be selected from input programs. For instance, a label “take changes proposed in program \mathcal{A} ” can correspond to a single code token as well as an entire method signature or body. As such, the merge types are not restrictive in their representation power of merge conflicts.

13 MERGE RESOLUTION DECODING

Here we provide additional implementation details about the model.

Each model prediction yields a probability distribution $p(r_j|a_j, b_j, o_j)$ over primitive merge patterns given a token-level conflict. In case

of a one-to-many correspondence between original line-level and the token-level conflicts (see, for instance, Fig. 6) to approximate the original $p(R|A, B, O)$ we decode the most promising combination from the predicted solution space. This can be conceptualized as a maximum cost path search on a matrix, which we approach via a beam search algorithm.

As a result, the model prediction for each line-level conflict consists of either a label for a token-level conflict or a combination of labels for multiple token-level conflicts representing the best prediction for each token-level conflict within the line-level conflict. Given these labels for each line-level conflict and the contents of the merged file, MergeBERT generates the code corresponding to the resolution region. The contents of the merged file includes the conflict in question and its surrounding regions. Therefore, for each conflicting line, MergeBERT chooses between the versions of code based on the labels the model produced and generates the resolution code by concatenating them. Afterwards, MergeBERT checks the syntax of the generated resolved code, and in case of correctness, outputs it as the candidate merge conflict resolution.

In case of multiple line-level conflicts in the merged file, MergeBERT refines the contents of the merged file that serves as the surrounding region of the conflict. More specifically, for each line-level conflict, MergeBERT replaces the other conflicts in the the merged file contents with the code it previously generated as their predicted resolutions. For this purpose, MergeBERT updates the contents of the merged file after resolving each line-level conflict with the code it generates as the conflict resolution based on the model prediction.

13.1 Multiple Conflicting Regions

MergeBERT can deal with non-trivial real-world merges, composed of multiple conflicting chunks. To provide an example of such a merge conflict, we include Fig. 6. MergeBERT correctly predicts a concatenation of changes proposed by developers A and B for the first token-level chunk and a concatenation of changes proposed by developers B and A (in the reverse order) for the second chunk.

14 USER STUDY INTERFACE

When a participant opens the interface, the system selects conflicts that the participant has previously resolved and populates the task list with three of them. Figure 7 show the list of conflicts as tasks for a sample participant.

Once a task is selected, the interface shows a page where they can view the conflict as well as their own resolution and resolution suggestions from MergeBERT. This is shown in Figure 8. They can also click on a link to take them to the merge commit in the GitHub repository and explore there if additional context is helpful.

For each resolution suggestion, the authors can indicate if the suggestion is an acceptable merge resolution or not. Based on their answer to this question, we ask additional followup questions, shown in table 7.

Participants can choose to skip the conflict and move to the next one if they desire. Figure 9 shows questions that we ask the participant to answer if they choose to skip a conflict.

Figure 5: Summary of merge conflict resolution labels in our dataset for TypeScript: label distribution for merge conflicts extracted with token-level differencing algorithm.

Algorithm 1 Merge conflict resolution decoding algorithm (beam search) with MergeBERT

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1536  $b \leftarrow \{r_0, 0\}$  ▷ Initialize beam {state, logprob}
1537  $\{a_j, b_j, o_j, r_j\}_{j=0 \dots N} \leftarrow \text{token\_diff3}(\mathcal{A}, \mathcal{B}, \mathcal{O}, \mathcal{M})$  ▷ Perform token-level differencing
1538 for  $j \leftarrow 0$  to  $N$  do
1539   if  $a_j = \emptyset \wedge b_j = \emptyset \wedge o_j = \emptyset$  then ▷ In case token-level merge results in a clean merge
1540     return  $\text{prefix}_j :: r_j :: \text{suffix}_j$ 
1541   else
1542     for  $(r_j^k, p_j^k) \in \text{TopK}(\text{MergeBERT}(r_j | a_j, b_j, o_j))$  do
1543        $b \leftarrow b \cup \{r + \text{prefix}_j :: r_j^k :: \text{suffix}_j, p + p_j^k\}$  ▷ Update beam for each token-level conflict  $j$ 
1544     end for
1545      $b \leftarrow \text{TopM}(b)$  ▷ Prune candidates to keep top-M
1546   end if
1547 end for
1548  $R \leftarrow b[0]$  ▷ Get resolution region string
1549 return  $R$ 

```

Table 7: User study questions rendered in the study interface depending on the scenario action taken by the participant. For example, if a participant evaluates a suggestion as 'acceptable' they would answer all questions listed under 'suggestion is acceptable'.

Scenario	User Study Questions
Suggestion is acceptable	1) Is this suggestion semantically equivalent to the user resolution? 2) Did the order of appearance of different statements play a factor in why you chose this suggestion? 3) Open Response
Suggestion is not acceptable	1) Is any external context needed in order to correctly resolve this conflict? 2) Open response
If additional code is added	1) Is the added code necessary in order to correctly resolve the merge conflict?
Skip this conflict	1) Multi-select option to explain why 2) Open response

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Var form = $(this);
settings.dom.bind(settings.event, function() {
    var status = false;
    var data = form.serialize();
    if(settings.fields){
<<<<<<< A.js
        data += '&' + $.param({'fields':settings.fields});
||||||| Base.js
        params.fields = settings.fields;
=====
        data += $.param({'fields':settings.fields});
>>>>>>> B.js
    }
    if (status && settings.submitHandler){
        return settings.submitHandler.apply(this);
    }
    Return status;
});
    
```

(a) Line-level conflict

```

var form = $(this);
settings.dom.bind(settings.event, function() {
    var status = false;
    var data = form.serialize();
    if (settings.fields) {
        data += '
<<<<<<< A.js
            data += '&' + $
||||||| Base.js
            params
=====
            data += $
>>>>>>> B.js
            .
<<<<<<< A.js
            param({'fields':
||||||| Base.js
            fields =
=====
            param({'fields:
>>>>>>> B.js
settings.fields});
        if (status && settings.submitHandler) {
            return settings.submitHandler.apply(this);
        }
        return status;
    });
    
```

(b) Token-level conflicts

```

Var form = $(this);
settings.dom.bind(settings.event, function() {
    var status = false;
    var data = form.serialize();
    if(settings.fields){
        data += $.param({'fields':settings.fields});
    }
    if (status && settings.submitHandler){
        return settings.submitHandler.apply(this);
    }
    Return status;
});
    
```

(c) Resolved merge

Figure 6: Example real-world merge conflict resolved by MergeBERT. (Top) merge conflict represented through the standard diff3, (middle) corresponding token-level conflicts, and (bottom) the user resolution.

Task List

Below is a list of recent merge conflicts pulled from the VSCode repository. For each conflicting file, evaluate the suggestions by clicking 'Begin'. You may complete the questions at your own pace, all progress will be saved.

- src/vs/workbench/contrib/terminal/common/terminal.ts (1 Merge Conflicts) [BEGIN]
- src/vs/workbench/contrib/terminal/browser/terminal.contribution.ts (1 Merge Conflicts) [COMPLETED]
- src/vs/workbench/contrib/terminal/browser/links/terminalWordLinkProvider.ts (2 Merge Conflicts) [BEGIN]

Figure 7: This is the main page of the user study interface. Each participant is shown a customized task list, based on merge conflicts they recently resolved.

microsoft / vscode

1 CONFLICT at src/vs/workbench/contrib/terminal/common/terminal.ts

Merge conflict created on Fri, 12 Mar 2021 15:47:24 +0000
 Author current branch [redacted]
 Author incoming branch [redacted]

User Resolution	Conflict File	Selected Resolution	CONFLICT
<p>Suggestion 1</p> <p>Suggestion 2</p> <p>Skip Conflict</p>	<pre> 402 NEW_IN_ACTIVE_WORKSPACE = 'workbench.action.terminal.newInactiveWorkspa 403 SPLIT = 'workbench.action.terminal.split', 404 SPLIT_IN_ACTIVE_WORKSPACE = 'workbench.action.terminal.splitInactiveWo 405 RELAUNCH = 'workbench.action.terminal.relaunch', 406 FOCUS_PREVIOUS_PANE = 'workbench.action.terminal.focusPreviousPane', 407 FOCUS_NEXT_PANE = 'workbench.action.terminal.focusNextPane', 408 RESIZE_PANE_LEFT = 'workbench.action.terminal.resizePaneLeft', 409 RESIZE_PANE_RIGHT = 'workbench.action.terminal.resizePaneRight', 410 RESIZE_PANE_UP = 'workbench.action.terminal.resizePaneUp', 411 RESIZE_PANE_DOWN = 'workbench.action.terminal.resizePaneDown', 412 FOCUS = 'workbench.action.terminal.focus', 413 FOCUS_NEXT = 'workbench.action.terminal.focusNext', 414 FOCUS_PREVIOUS = 'workbench.action.terminal.focusPrevious', 415 PASTE = 'workbench.action.terminal.paste', 416----- CURRENT 417 PASTE_SELECTION = 'workbench.action.terminal.pasteSelection', 418- SELECT_DEFAULT_SHELL = 'workbench.action.terminal.selectDefaultShell', 419----- 420 SELECT_DEFAULT_PROFILE = 'workbench.action.terminal.selectDefaultShe 421----- INCORPORATING </pre>	<pre> 402 NEW_IN_ACTIVE_WORKSPACE = 'workbench.action.terminal.newInactiveWorkspa 403 SPLIT = 'workbench.action.terminal.split', 404 SPLIT_IN_ACTIVE_WORKSPACE = 'workbench.action.terminal.splitInactiveWo 405 RELAUNCH = 'workbench.action.terminal.relaunch', 406 FOCUS_PREVIOUS_PANE = 'workbench.action.terminal.focusPreviousPane', 407 FOCUS_NEXT_PANE = 'workbench.action.terminal.focusNextPane', 408 RESIZE_PANE_LEFT = 'workbench.action.terminal.resizePaneLeft', 409 RESIZE_PANE_RIGHT = 'workbench.action.terminal.resizePaneRight', 410 RESIZE_PANE_UP = 'workbench.action.terminal.resizePaneUp', 411 RESIZE_PANE_DOWN = 'workbench.action.terminal.resizePaneDown', 412 FOCUS = 'workbench.action.terminal.focus', 413 FOCUS_NEXT = 'workbench.action.terminal.focusNext', 414 FOCUS_PREVIOUS = 'workbench.action.terminal.focusPrevious', 415 PASTE = 'workbench.action.terminal.paste', 416 PASTE_SELECTION = 'workbench.action.terminal.pasteSelection', 417 SELECT_DEFAULT_PROFILE = 'workbench.action.terminal.selectDefaultShe </pre>	<p>CONFLICT < 1 / 1 ></p>

425 SCROLL_DOWN_LINE = 'workbench.action.terminal.scrollDown',
 426 SCROLL_DOWN_PAGE = 'workbench.action.terminal.scrollDownPage',
 427 SCROLL_TO_BOTTOM = 'workbench.action.terminal.scrollToBottom',
 428 SCROLL_UP_LINE = 'workbench.action.terminal.scrollUp',
 429 SCROLL_UP_PAGE = 'workbench.action.terminal.scrollUpPage',
 430 SCROLL_TO_TOP = 'workbench.action.terminal.scrollToTop',
 431 CLEAR = 'workbench.action.terminal.clear',

Skip this Conflict

1 Please pick one or more reasons that influenced your decision

- Conflict is too large
- Conflict is too complex
- I need help from a colleague
- Other

2 Please leave any additional comments/reasons for your decision

[Text input field]

Figure 8: After selecting a file from the task list, participants are taken to a page where they can view the conflict file, their original resolution, as well as the resolution suggestions generated by MergeBERT. Participants click on suggestions to evaluate them, or opt to skip a conflict within a file. Participants directly fill out survey questions in a form at the bottom of the page.

Figure 9: Example of questions rendered for the 'Skip Conflict' option.